

A Foundational Schema.org Mapping for a Legal Knowledge Graph: Representing Brazilian Legal Norms as FRBR Works

Hudson de Martim¹

¹Federal Senate of Brazil , hudsonm@senado.leg.br

Abstract

Structuring legal norms for machine readability is a critical prerequisite for building advanced AI and information retrieval systems, such as Legal Knowledge Graphs (LKGs). Grounded in the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) model, this paper proposes a foundational mapping for the abstract legal *Work*—which is materialized as the *Norm* node in our legal Graph RAG framework [1]—to the interoperable `schema.org/Legislation` vocabulary. Using the `Normas.leg.br` portal as a practical case study, we demonstrate how to describe this *Work* entity via JSON-LD, considering stable URN identifiers, inter-norm relationships, and lifecycle properties. This structured, formal approach provides the essential first step toward creating a deterministic and verifiable knowledge graph, which can serve as a formalized "ground truth" for Legal AI applications, overcoming the limitations of purely probabilistic models.

Keywords: Legal Knowledge Graph, Data Modeling, Schema.org, Linked Data, FRBR, Information Retrieval, Legal AI.

1 Introduction

Open Government Data (OGD) initiatives are fundamental for enhancing transparency and public participation by making government-generated information openly accessible. However, while the principles of OGD are well established, their application to the legal domain presents unique and significant challenges. Legal norms are not static data points. They are complex, structured documents with a dynamic lifecycle, characterized by a formal hierarchy, extensive inter-norm references, and continuous evolution through temporal versions.

Simply publishing legal texts as open files (e.g., PDF or plain text) fails to capture this rich semantic structure, hindering the development of advanced Legal Tech and AI applications that require machine-readable data. To bridge this gap, this paper details a structured, standardized mapping for Brazilian legal norms using the widely adopted Schema.org vocabulary. We focus specifically on modeling the legal norm as a conceptual *Work*, thereby establishing the foundational layer for a more comprehensive and deterministic representation of legal knowledge.

1.1 The Significance of Open Government Data

Open Government Data (OGD) initiatives are pivotal for enhancing transparency, accountability, and innovation by publishing public-sector information without restrictions [2]. By making data produced with public funds freely available, governments can stimulate economic growth, improve internal workflows, and empower citizens to participate in policymaking [3]. This principle of openness is especially relevant in the legal domain, though, as we will discuss, it presents unique structural challenges.

1.2 The Challenge of Structuring Legal Norms for Machine Readability

While OGD principles provide the "why," the nature of legal data dictates the "how." Unlike tabular data, legal norms possess a deep, hierarchical structure (e.g., titles, chapters, articles) and evolve over time through amendments and repeals. This temporal dynamism means that the "correct" text of a law is dependent on a specific point in time [4]. Furthermore, the dense web of citations and references between norms creates a complex graph of relationships that is essential for correct interpretation but is lost in unstructured formats.

This lack of structured, machine-readable data remains a critical bottleneck for advancing Legal Tech applications, such as Legal Knowledge Graphs (LKGs) and sophisticated AI-powered retrieval systems. These systems require a deterministic, verifiable "ground truth" of the law, which cannot be achieved without a formal data model [1].

1.3 Our Contribution: A Schema.org Mapping for Brazilian Legal Works

To address these challenges, and focusing on the Normas.leg.br portal initiative by the Brazilian National Congress, we propose a unified mapping of Brazilian legislation to the `schema.org/Legislation` vocabulary via JSON-LD and Linked Data. Our approach centers on the foundational concept of the legal **Work**.

This paper's core contribution is the detailed specification of how a conceptual legal norm, understood as an abstract **Work**—and materialized as *Norm* node in our legal Graph RAG framework [1]— can be mapped to `sdo:Legislation`. This entity represents the legal instrument in its entirety, independent of specific textual versions or formats. We detail the key properties for describing this legal *Work*, providing concrete examples based on Brazilian law and considering URN identifiers, multilingual support, and inter-norm relationships. This structured schema serves as the essential first layer for improving the quality and interoperability of Brazilian legal data, laying the groundwork for a scalable Legal Knowledge Graph. Subsequent work will build upon this foundation to model the norm's internal components (*Component Works*) and their dynamic temporal versions, as outlined in our framework.

2 Fundamental Concepts

To effectively leverage legal norms in automated systems, we must move beyond plain text to structured, machine-readable formats. This structured data is the bedrock for the modern Legal Tech sector, which develops tools to manage and analyze legal information at scale [5]. Specifically, Legal Knowledge Graphs (LKGs)—which model legal entities and their relationships as graph structures—depend on semantically rich and interoperable data to enable sophisticated queries and automated inference [6, 7].

This section outlines the foundational standards and principles our work is built upon: the practical context of the Normas.leg.br project and the technical cornerstones of Linked Data and the Schema.org vocabulary.

2.1 The Normas.leg.br Project: A Practical Implementation

The **Normas.leg.br** portal¹, maintained by the Brazilian National Congress, embodies OGD principles by granting unrestricted access to federal norms' full texts and metadata. To move beyond simple access and enable advanced processing and interoperability, the project strategically adopted international standards as its foundation [8]. This approach, centered on the principles of Linked Data and the Schema.org vocabulary,

¹Normas.leg.br is a portal developed by the Brazilian National Congress providing free, structured access to federal legislation. It offers metadata for all norms and compiled texts for many, especially recent ones. The portal is a practical application of the principles discussed in this paper. Available at: <https://normas.leg.br>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

aims to make Brazilian norms easily discoverable, linkable, and integrable into a global Legal Knowledge Graph [9, 1].

2.2 Foundational Principles and Vocabularies

2.2.1 The Linked Data Principles

The Normas.leg.br initiative implements the four core principles of Linked Data to publish Brazilian legal metadata in an open, machine-readable format [10]:

1. **Use URIs to name everything.** Assign a unique URI to each legal norm, ensuring unambiguous identification.
2. **Use HTTP(S) URIs.** Publish these identifiers so they can be accessed and managed over the Web.
3. **Make URIs dereferenceable.** Configure each URI to return machine-readable metadata about the identified resource.
4. **Include links to other URIs.** Create relationships between legal entities to form a web of interconnected data.

These principles ensure clarity in identifier management and lay the groundwork for a seamless integration of Brazilian legislation into a global LKG.

2.2.2 Schema.org Vocabulary for Legal Norms

To describe the resources identified by URIs, we use **Schema.org**², a shared, collaborative vocabulary for structured data. We leverage its hierarchical structure, starting from the generic `Thing` type, which defines basic properties like `name` and `sameAs`.

For our specific context, we use two key types:

- **CreativeWork:** A broad class for creative outputs, which serves as the parent for legal documents.
- **Legislation:** A specialization of `CreativeWork` designed to model legal norms. It introduces essential properties such as `legislationIdentifier` (for a unique ID, like a URN), `legislationDate` (enactment date), and `legislationType` (e.g., law, decree). These properties enable the structured description required for machine processing and analysis. It is important to note that the `schema.org/Legislation` vocabulary was heavily inspired by the European Legislation Identifier (ELI) ontology, a standard designed to foster interoperability of legal information across European jurisdictions [11]. This connection underscores the maturity of the model and its suitability for building standardized LKGs.

Figure 1 presents simplified diagrams of this vocabulary, illustrating how `Legislation` and its related types are used in our proposed mapping—the cardinalities of the relationships have been adapted to reflect this mapping. These diagrams clarify how `Legislation` and its subcomponents integrate into the broader Legal Knowledge Graph schema.

²Schema.org is a collaborative project providing a shared vocabulary for structured data markup on the internet, primarily used to help search engines understand web content. The project Portal can be accessed at <https://schema.org/>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

Figure 1: Simplified diagram of the Schema.org vocabulary, according to the proposed mapping in this work.

3 Mapping the Legal Work to `sdo:Legislation`

The cornerstone of any robust Legal Knowledge Graph is a formal model that can handle the identity of legal norms as they persist through time and across different formats. To achieve this, we adopt a core concept from the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) framework, as detailed in [4]: the distinction between the abstract intellectual content and its textual realization [12].

Following this model, we distinguish between three core entities. First, an abstract **Work** is a distinct intellectual creation—the law’s conceptual essence (e.g., the "1988 Brazilian Federal Constitution")—independent of any specific wording. This *Work* (materialized as *Norm* node in our Graph RAG framework [1]) is realized through one or more **Expressions**, which are the specific textual versions of the law, such as its original text or a later amended version. Finally, an *Expression* is embodied in a **Manifestation**, the physical or digital format in which it is published (e.g., a PDF file or an HTML web page). In this paper, we focus on the foundational *Work*, which serves as the stable, top-level anchor node in our knowledge graph, to which all components and versions will eventually be linked.

To represent this abstract *Work* using a widely-understood, interoperable vocabulary, we turn to Schema.org. While a legal norm could be generally typed as an `sdo:CreativeWork` (the superclass of most content types), Schema.org provides a more specific and semantically rich subclass: `sdo:Legislation`.

The definition of `sdo:Legislation` as "a legal act, enforceable or not..."³ provides an initial alignment with our conceptual *Work* entity. Fundamentally, this alignment is further reinforced by its data properties: `sdo:Legislation` offers properties such as `sdo:jurisdiction` (e.g., "Brazil"), `sdo:legislationType` (e.g., "Federal Constitution"), and `sdo:legislationIdentifier` (e.g., the URN). These properties correspond directly to the persistent, high-level metadata of the abstract legal *Work*, which remain constant across all its temporal versions (*Expressions*). This strong alignment in both definition and data structure makes `sdo:Legislation` an ideal and precise choice for modeling the top-level *Work* entity. In this foundational step, we use it exclusively to model the norm as a whole (the *Norm* node in our framework).

Table 1 presents the key properties for describing a `sdo:Legislation` instance when it represents a legal *Work* (*Norm* node). We detail the mapping for Brazilian legal norms using “Lei Complementar nº 123 de 14/12/2006” (Complementary Law No. 123 of 2006-12-14)⁴ as a running example.

³The Legislation Type can be accessed at <https://schema.org/Legislation>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

⁴The general metadata of the Brazilian legal norm "Lei Complementar nº 123 de 14/12/2006" (Complementary Law No. 123

Table 1: Properties of a `sdo:Legislation` instance representing a legal *Work*, with mapping descriptions for Brazilian norms and examples from "Lei Complementar nº 123 de 14/12/2006" (Complementary Law No. 123 of 2006-12-14).

Properties	Mapping	Examples
<code>id</code>	The dereferenceable URI identifying the legal <i>Work</i> . It is based on the format <code>https://normas.leg.br/?urn=<legislationIdentifier></code> The <code><legislationIdentifier></code> property is presented below.	<code>"https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123"</code>
<code>legislationType</code>	The formal category of the <i>Work</i> ^{5 6} .	A <code>CategoryCode</code> : <pre>{ "@type": "CategoryCode", "@id": "https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:tipo.norma:lei.complementar" }</pre>
<code>legislationIdentifier</code>	The canonical URN of the legal <i>Work</i> , according to the format proposed by the LexML project – found at <code>https://projeto.lexml.gov.br/</code>	<code>"urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123"</code>
<code>sameAs</code>	List of alternative URLs for the legal <i>Work</i> . Optional. For example, the URL of the norm for the LexML portal or for the portal of the associated legislative/executive House can be included.	<code>["https://www.lexml.gov.br/urn/urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123", "https://legis.senado.leg.br/legislacao/DetalhaSigen.action?id=572878"]</code>

of 2006-12-14) can be visualized at <https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123>. The general metadata are presented in a structured format in the information panel (on the right side of the page). Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

⁵Although [1] suggests that "For a more precise representation... specialized entity types... can be created..." (e.g., "Constituição Federal," "Lei Ordinária"), the standard Schema.org/Legislation vocabulary does not directly offer such fine-grained, pre-defined subtypes. Therefore, this work employs the `legislationType` property to explicitly denote the specific category of the legal norm, effectively achieving a similar level of differentiation as proposed specializations.

⁶The set of possible values for types of Brazilian legislation can be found in the `CategoryCodeSet` declaration located at <https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:conceito:tipo.norma>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

inLanguage	Code of the language, according to the IETF BCP 47 standard, in which the legal <i>Work</i> 's metadata is described. If names or descriptions are provided in other languages, these should also be included.	A simple value or a list of languages: "pt" Or ["pt", "en"]
name	The formal title (epigraph) of the legal <i>Work</i> with its enactment date in DD/M-M/YYYY format. Populate using upper and lower case, even if the epigraph appears in all uppercase in the original text, including changing 'N°' to 'n°'.	A simple value or a list of language-localized values: "Lei Complementar n° 123 de 14/12/2006" Or [{"@value": "Lei Complementar n° 123 de 14/12/2006", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "Complementary Law n° 123 of 2006-12-14", "@language": "en"}]
alternateName	List of common or informal names for the legal <i>Work</i> . Optional.	A simple list or a list of language-localized values: ["Lei do Supersimples", "Lei Geral das Micro e Pequenas Empresas"] Or [{"@value": "Lei do Supersimples", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "Law of Supersimple", "@language": "en"}, {"@value": "Lei Geral das Micro e Pequenas Empresas", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "General Law of Micro and Small Enterprises", "@language": "en"}]

abstract

The official summary (ementa) of the legal *Work*. Optional.

A simple value or a list of language-localized values:

```
"Institui o Estatuto Nacional da Microempresa e da Empresa de Pequeno Porte; altera dispositivos das Leis n°s 8.212 e 8.213, ambas de 24 de julho de 1991, da Consolidação das Leis do Trabalho - CLT, aprovada..."
```

Or

```
[{"@value": "Institui...", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "Establish...", "@language": "en"}]
```

keywords

List of keywords for indexing the legal *Work*. Optional.

A simple list or a list of language-localized values:

```
["Pequena Empresa", "Microempresa"]
```

Or

```
[{"@value": "Pequena Empresa", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "Small Enterprise", "@language": "en"}, {"@value": "Microempresa", "@language": "pt"}, {"@value": "Micro enterprise", "@language": "en"}]
```

<code>about</code>	List of classification themes for the legal <i>Work</i> ⁷ . Optional. The value of the <code>name</code> property can be provided, for display purposes, when the source doesn't have a structured Schema.org description for the object.	Hypothetical example: <pre>{ "@type": "DefinedTerm", "@id": "https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:tema:direito.empresarial.e.economico" }</pre>
<code>legislationDate</code>	The date of enactment (signature), marking the creation of the legal <i>Work</i> in YYYY-MM-DD format. Temporal description of the norm's creation event (derived from <code>dateCreated</code>).	"2006-12-14"
<code>legislationPassedBy</code>	The legislative body that approved the legal <i>Work</i> . Spatial (derived from <code>locationCreated</code>) and Institutional (agent) description of the norm's creation event.	<pre>{ "@type": "GovernmentOrganization", "@id": "https://www.congressonacional.leg.br/" }</pre>
<code>spatialCoverage</code>	The geographical area of applicability. It can be, for example, the country, a state, a municipality ⁸ . The value of the <code>name</code> property can be provided, for display purposes, when the source doesn't have a structured Schema.org description for the object.	<pre>{ "@type": "Country", "@id": "https://servicodados.ibge.gov.br/api/v1/localidades/paises/76", "name": "Brasil (país)", "url": "https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q155", "address": { "@type": "PostalAddress", "addressCountry": "BR" } }</pre>

⁷The set of possible values for themes of Brazilian legislation can be found at <https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:conceito:tema>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

⁸As the URI for Brazilian locations, the official registry of IBGE (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics) can be used: <https://servicodados.ibge.gov.br/api/docs/localidades>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

<code>legislationJurisdiction</code>	<p>This property identifies the political or administrative entity that holds the legal authority to promulgate the legislative instrument. It pertains to the concept of sovereignty and competence, answering the question "who" is the source of the law's power, rather than "where" the law applies, which is addressed by <code>spatialCoverage</code>. For example, a federal law could originate from the federal jurisdiction of the Union, but its <code>spatialCoverage</code> could be restricted to the specific territory of the Manaus Free Trade Zone ("Zona Franca de Manaus"). For federal law, the jurisdiction is the federal union; for state law, it is the respective state etc.</p>	<pre>{ "@type": "AdministrativeArea", "@id": "https://www.wiki data.org/wiki/Q5440531", "name": "Governo Federal do Brasil (União)"} </pre>
<code>datePublished</code>	<p>The publication date of the original version of the legal <i>Work</i>, in YYYY-MM-DD format. Temporal description of the norm's publication event.</p>	"2006-12-15"
<code>publisher</code>	<p>The official publisher of the original version of the legal <i>Work</i>. Spatial (<code>locationPublished</code>) and Institutional (agent) description of the norm's publication event.</p>	<pre>{ "@type": "GovernmentOrganization", "@id": "https://www.in.gov.br/" } </pre>
<code>license</code>	<p>License for the publication of the original version of the legal <i>Work</i>.</p>	" http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/ "
<code>legislationLegalForce</code>	<p>Indicates whether this legal <i>Work</i> is currently in force. Optional. Should only be specified, with "NotInForce", when the norm is not currently in force.</p>	"NotInForce" (Hypothetical example)

<code>temporalCoverage</code>	<p>Period during which this legal <i>Work</i> was in force. Optional.</p> <p>According to project ELI⁹: "in force range of the act, from the date it was set in force to the date it was repealed." Should only be specified when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • this legal <i>Work</i> is not currently in force (e.g., "2006-12-20/2010-01-05"); • the legal <i>Work</i>'s effective date differs from its default start validity date (e.g., "2006-12-20/.."). <p>May contain multiple non-continuous periods (e.g., ["2006-12-20/2010-01-05", "2012-05-05/.."]) (International Standard ISO 8601).</p>	"2006-12-14/2018-03-30"
<code>legislationDateOfApplicability</code>	<p>The date at which the legal <i>Work</i> becomes applicable. Optional.</p> <p>Should only be specified when this date is different from the date of entry into force - for example, a legal <i>Work</i> may come in force today, and state it will become applicable in 3 months.</p>	"2007-03-14" (Hypothetical example)
<code>sdPublisher</code>	Publisher of the structured data for this legal <i>Work</i> .	{ "@type": "GovernmentOrganization", "@id": "https://www.congressional.leg.br/" }
<code>sdDatePublished</code>	Date of publication of the structured data for this legal <i>Work</i> , in YYYY-MM-DD format.	"2021-10-04"
<code>sdLicense</code>	License for the publication of the structured data for this legal <i>Work</i> .	"http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"

To illustrate how the properties detailed in Table 1 come together, Listing 1 presents a complete JSON-LD document¹⁰ for the legal *Work* "Lei Complementar nº 123 de 14/12/2006". This example demonstrates a structured representation of the *Norm* entity/node according to the Schema.org vocabulary. While some property values are hypothetical for didactic purposes, the structure reflects the proposed mapping.

⁹The European Legislation Identifier (ELI) standard, whose ontology was a key input for the Schema.org/Legislation vocabulary. For more details, see the official documentation [11].

¹⁰The JSON-LD examples can be tested using the Schema.org validator: <https://validator.schema.org/>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

The example also highlights three key JSON-LD properties that are essential for creating linked data:

- `@context`: Maps the terms used in the document (e.g., "name", "legislationDate") to their full IRIs in the Schema.org vocabulary.
- `@type`: Explicitly declares the resource's type, in this case, `sdo:Legislation`.
- `@id`: Provides a unique, global identifier (URI) for the resource being described, making it linkable from anywhere on the web.

Listing 1: A json-LD with general Legislation properties of the Brazilian legal *Work* Complementary Law No. 123 of 2006-12-14.

```
{
  "@context": "http://schema.org/",
  "@type": "Legislation",
  "@id": "https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123",
  "legislationType": {
    "@type": "CategoryCode",
    "@id": "https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:tipo-norma:lei.complementar"
  },
  "legislationIdentifier": "urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123",
  "sameAs": [
    "http://www.lexml.gov.br/urn/urn:lex:br:federal:lei.complementar:2006-12-14;123",
    "http://legis.senado.leg.br/legislacao/DetalhaSigen.action?id=572878"
  ],
  "inLanguage": "pt",
  "name": "Lei Complementar n° 123 de 14/12/2006",
  "alternateName": [
    "LCP-123-2006-12-14",
    "Lei do Supersimples",
    "Lei Geral das Micro e Pequenas Empresas"
  ],
  "abstract": "Institui o Estatuto Nacional da Microempresa e da Empresa de Pequeno Porte; altera dispositivos ...",
  "about": {
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "@id": "https://normas.leg.br/?urn=urn:lex:br:federal:tema:direito.empresarial.e.economico"
  },
  "keywords": [
    "Microempresa",
    "Pequena Empresa"
  ],
  "legislationDate": "2006-12-14",
  "legislationPassedBy": {
    "@type": "GovernmentOrganization",
    "@id": "https://www.congressonacional.leg.br/"
  },
  "legislationJurisdiction": {
    "@type": "AdministrativeArea",
    "@id": "https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5440531",
    "name": "Governo Federal do Brasil (Uniao)"
  },
  "spatialCoverage": {
    "@type": "Country",
    "@id": "https://servicodados.ibge.gov.br/api/v1/localidades/paises/76",
    "name": "Brasil",
    "url": "https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q155",
    "address": {
      "@type": "PostalAddress",
      "addressCountry": "BR"
    }
  },
  "datePublished": "2006-12-15",
  "license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
  "publisher": {
    "@type": "GovernmentOrganization",
    "@id": "https://www.in.gov.br/"
  },
  "sdDatePublished": "2024-10-04",
  "sdLicense": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
  "sdPublisher": {
    "@type": "GovernmentOrganization",
    "@id": "https://www.congressonacional.leg.br/"
  }
}
```

4 Conclusion and Future Work

Building upon our broader data modeling strategy for legal norms, this paper has detailed the foundational mapping for the FRBR framework's concept of a legal *Work* [4]—materialized as a *Norm* node in our

legal Graph RAG framework [1]. By specifying a concrete implementation of this abstract entity using the interoperable `sdo:Legislation` vocabulary, we provide a practical solution to the challenge of representing the stable identity of legal acts. This mapping serves as the central anchor for the entire knowledge graph, establishing a deterministic "ground truth" to which all other temporal versions, linguistic variations, and structural components can be linked.

This approach is critical for Legal AI, as it provides a verifiable foundation that contrasts with the purely probabilistic nature of large language models. The key contributions of this work are:

- **A detailed, property-by-property mapping** of the legal *Work (Norm)* entity to `sdo:Legislation`, demonstrated with a practical JSON-LD implementation for the Brazilian legal system.
- **A scalable and interoperable foundation** for a temporally-aware Legal Knowledge Graph, enabling the development of more reliable and precise AI-driven tools for legal analysis.

By making the core identity of legal information machine-readable in a standardized way, this work facilitates significant advancements in legal information retrieval and decision support systems.

For future work, this well-defined *Work (Norm)* entity serves as the cornerstone for modeling the full complexity of legal norms. As outlined in [4], the immediate next steps involve the structured description of *Component Works* and their versioning through *Temporal* and *Language Expressions*, materialized as the *Component* and *Version* nodes in our legal Graph RAG framework [1]. Ultimately, exploring the practical application of this multi-layered LKG in structure-aware retrieval systems for legal professionals and citizens remains a promising and vital avenue for research.

References

- [1] De Martim H. Graph RAG for legal norms: A hierarchical and temporal approach. [preprint]. arXiv:2505.00039; 2025.
- [2] Ubaldi B. Open government data: Towards empirical analysis of open government data initiatives. Paris: OECD Publishing; 2013.
- [3] Lathrop D, Ruma L. Open government: Collaboration, transparency, and participation in practice. Sebastopol: O'Reilly Media; 2010.
- [4] De Martim H. A temporal FRBR/FRBRoo-based model for component-level versioning of legal norms. [preprint]. arXiv:2506.07853; 2025.
- [5] Veith C, Bandlow M, Harnisch M, Wenzler H, Hartung M, Hartung D. How legal technology will change the business of law. Boston: Boston Consulting Group & Bucerius Law School; 2016.
- [6] Filtz E. Building and processing a knowledge-graph for legal data. In: Proceedings of the Semantic Web: 14th International Conference, ESWC 2017; 2017 May 28-Jun 1; Portorož, Slovenia. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2017. p. 184-94.
- [7] Koniaris M, Papastefanatos G, Vassiliou Y. Towards automatic structuring and semantic indexing of legal documents. In: Proceedings of the 20th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics; 2016. p. 1-6.
- [8] De Martim H. Normas jurídicas brasileiras integradas a um Legal Knowledge Graph (LKG) global: uma abordagem baseada na proposta Schema.org/Legislation. Brasília: Senado Federal, Instituto Legislativo Brasileiro; 2019. Available at: <https://www2.senado.gov.br/bdsf/handle/id/600722>. Last accessed on 2025-04-19.

- [9] Bizer C, Heath T, Idehen K, Berners-Lee T. Linked data on the web (LDOW2008). In: Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on World Wide Web; 2008. p. 1265-6.
- [10] Bizer C, Heath T, Berners-Lee T. Linked data: Principles and state of the art. In: Proceedings of the World Wide Web Conference; 2008. p. 40.
- [11] Publications Office of the European Union. ELI: European Legislation Identifier – How to implement ELI; 2021 [cited 2025 Apr 20]. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli-register/implement.html>
- [12] Bekiari C, Doerr M, Le Bœuf P, Riva P. FRBRoo: A Conceptual Model for Bibliographic Information in Object-Oriented Formalism. Version 2.4. International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA); 2015. Available at: https://www.ifla.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/assets/cataloguing/frbr-rg/frbroo_v_2.4.pdf.